

ImproRisk

“Exposure Assessment in Acrylamide”

ImproRisk Scientific Report

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1 Summary

Acrylamide is a low molecular weight, highly water soluble, organic compound. It was discovered that it forms when certain foods are prepared at temperatures usually above 120 °C and low moisture. It forms, at least in part, due to a Maillard reaction between certain amino acids, such as asparagine, and reducing sugars. Acrylamide forms in numerous baked or fried carbohydrate-rich foods, including French fries, potato crisps, breads, biscuits and coffee. EFSA performed benchmark dose (BMD) analyses on data for neurotoxicity and on the tumour incidences induced by AA in experimental animals.

In the current report the dietary exposure of the target population is studied using ImproRisk model v.0.3.2. The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the dietary Acrylamide intake of the population in Cyprus, to carry out the necessary risk characterization and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the Acrylamide exposure.

Mean dietary Acrylamide exposure of the Cypriot population was calculated as 0.41 and 1.19 µg/kg b.w./day for mean and high consumers, respectively. Current exposure levels of Cypriot population are not of health concern with regards to neurotoxicity, and indicate some concern for carcinogenicity.

Fried potatoes, bread, cereal flakes, crisps/ships, roast potatoes and biscuits were the food categories with the highest contribution to the Acrylamide intake.

2 Introduction

Acrylamide is a colorless and odorless crystalline powder with a melting point of $\sim 85^{\circ}\text{C}$. It is readily soluble in water, acetone and ethanol. Acrylamide is the monomer used for the manufacture of polyacrylamide or its copolymers. Polyacrylamide is used mainly for water treatment, cosmetics, and in paper, petroleum and textile industries. Since 2002, high concentrations of acrylamide have been determined in various heat-processed food that evoke an international health alarm. Acrylamide forms, at least in part, due to a Maillard reaction between certain amino acids, such as asparagine, and reducing sugars. Acrylamide forms in numerous baked or fried carbohydrate-rich foods, including French fries, potato crisps, breads, biscuits and coffee. Acrylamide is also known to be present in cigarette smoke.

The toxicological properties of acrylamide have been well studied. It has been classified as probably carcinogen to humans by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC). Exposure of acrylamide at high levels causes damage to the nervous system. Based on in vitro and in vivo mammalian studies, acrylamide is also considered as a reproductive toxic chemical with mutagenic and carcinogenic properties. Although there is potential health risk of acrylamide in food, no maximum levels have been established for acrylamide in processed food. This is because acrylamide is formed by heat processing of food and it is difficult to treat it as a contaminant, since most of the acrylamide present in food is formed during household cooking. In 2007, the European Commission launched a Recommendation that the Member States should perform the monitoring of acrylamide in foodstuffs that are known to contain high acrylamide levels and/or contribute significantly to human exposure.

In order to carry out risk characterization, the Margin of Exposure (MOE) approach is applied. MOE is calculated as the Benchmark Dose Level (BMDL) value divided by the respective intake. EFSA has selected BMDL₁₀ values of 0.43 mg/kg b.w. per day for peripheral neuropathy in rats and of 0.17 mg/kg b.w. per day for neoplastic effects in mice.

2.1 Background

Two previous exposure assessments of Acrylamide have been performed using the excel based version of the ImproRisk either food consumption data obtained from the Child Health Database for adolescents (11-15 years) developed in 2003 in Cyprus or the consumption data obtained from the EUMenu project carried out in the years 2014-2018. In both cases, occurrence and consumption data were codified using the FoodEx1 classification system.

2.2 Terms of Reference

The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the dietary Acrylamide intake of the population in Cyprus, to carry out the necessary risk characterization and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the Acrylamide exposure. Acrylamide is considered to be neurotoxic in humans and is classified as a probable human carcinogen.

3 Data and Methodology

3.1 Occurrence data

Acrylamide occurrence data in food were extracted from LIMS for the years 2008-2020. For results below LOD, EFSA's assumption was applied. Since, in all cases left-censored results were below 50%, occurrence results below the LOD were set to half the LOD for the Middle-bound scenario. Dilution factors were applied on coffee concentrations in order to estimate concentrations for different coffee beverages. The aggregated occurrence contained 61 food items.

3.2 Consumption data

Food consumption data were obtained from the EUMenu project funded by EFSA and the dietary survey was carried out in the years 2014-2018. The consumption data was the result of a survey of 1661 participants (male and female). The survey covered all five cities of Cyprus, rural and urban regions, and also all days of the week and the four seasons. The population classes and the number of participants in each class were: [a] infants: 3-11 months (269), [b] toddlers: 12-35 months (279), [c] other children: 3-9 years (300), [d] adolescents: 10-17 years (274), [e] adults: 18-64 years (275) and [f] elderly: 65-74 years (264). The consumption dataset contained 82921 occasions.

3.3 Food classification

Consumption and occurrence data were both codified according to the FoodEx2 classification system developed by EFSA. At the moment of the generation of the present report the MTX catalogue version 13.1 was applied.

3.4 Methodologies

3.4.1 Chronic dietary exposure

Dietary exposure was assessed at individual level by multiplying the average daily consumption of each food with the corresponding mean occurrence estimated for Acrylamide summing up the respective intakes throughout the diet and finally dividing the results by the individual's body weight.

3.4.2 Dietary exposure assessment model

Dietary exposure assessment was performed using ImproRisk model version 0.3.2

4 Dietary Exposure Assessment

Table 4.1: Substance information

key	
Chemical Substance	Acrylamide
Substance Category	Contaminant
Reference value	430 µg/Kg b.w. per day
Type of reference value	Benchmark Dose Level (BMDL)

Table 4.2: Summary exposure statistics of Acrylamide

Scenario			
key	LB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)	MB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)	UB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)
Min	0	0	0
Max	4.523	4.528	4.534
Mean	0.404	0.406	0.407
SD	0.413	0.414	0.415
P25	0.133	0.134	0.135
Median	0.275	0.276	0.277
P75	0.532	0.534	0.535
P95	1.184	1.186	1.187
MoE ¹	1063.4	1060.3	1057.4
MoE ²	420.4	419.2	418.0

* MoE : Margin of Exposure, 1: neurotoxicity and 2: carcinogenicity

Mean and 95th percentile exposure were calculated as 0.41 and 1.19 µg/kg b.w. per day (Table 4.2). The above values are comparable to the corresponding exposure estimates for Cyprus (0.7 and 1.4 µg/kg b.w. per day, respectively), calculated by EFSA.

MOEs for neurotoxicity obtained for the current exposure to Acrylamide (Table 4.2) are above the MOE of 125, which is considered a safety margin for no health concern. Regarding

neoplastic effects, the fact that the calculated MOE values are substantially lower than 10000 indicates a health concern for carcinogenicity. Similar results were obtained by EFSA. It should be noted, though, that the BMDL for carcinogenicity (170 $\mu\text{g}/\text{Kg}$ b.w. per day) was based on data on the carcinogenic action of Acrylamide on the Harderian gland of rodents, an organ not found in the human body.

4.1 Distribution of exposure

Probability distribution

Figure 4.1 shows the probability distribution of the exposure.

Figure 4.1: Probability distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

Figure 4.1 shows the distribution of exposure of the Cypriot population based on mean occurrence. It can be shown that more than 98% of the population was exposed to Acrylamide less than 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{Kg}$ bw per day.

Cumulative distribution

Figure 4.2 shows the cumulative distribution of exposure.

Figure 4.2: Cumulative distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

4.2 Mean Exposure at the MB by Gender

Table 4.3: Summary exposure statistics Gender at MB scenario.

Gender	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	MoE
FEMALE	0	3.335	0.372	0.368	0.138	0.258	0.453	1.149	1,156.309
MALE	0	4.528	0.441	0.454	0.123	0.299	0.596	1.242	975.993

Table 4.3 and Figure 4.3 shows that there is no significant difference between the two genders meaning same food consumption habits for male and female subjects.

Figure 4.3: Mean Exposure by Gender at MB scenario.

4.3 Mean Exposure at the MB by Area

Table 4.4: Summary exposure statistics by Area at MB scenario.

Area	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	MoE
Ammochostos	0	2.917	0.430	0.386	0.174	0.345	0.566	1.179	1,000.957
Larnaka	0	3.587	0.374	0.379	0.120	0.250	0.490	1.057	1,150.246
Lefkosia	0	3.335	0.406	0.429	0.148	0.267	0.507	1.201	1,057.822
Lemesos	0	4.528	0.427	0.445	0.141	0.295	0.580	1.246	1,007.900
Pafos	0	2.292	0.401	0.375	0.089	0.270	0.583	1.186	1,072.833

Figure 4.4: Mean Exposure by Area at MB scenario.

4.4 Mean Exposure at the MB by Population Class

Table 4.5: Summary exposure statistics by Population Class at MB scenario.

Population class	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	MoE
Adolescents	0.037	3.072	0.530	0.454	0.207	0.408	0.725	1.400	810.573
Adults	0.007	2.130	0.337	0.314	0.118	0.242	0.438	0.974	1,277.597
Elderly	0.016	1.186	0.245	0.223	0.099	0.178	0.308	0.766	1,757.806
Infants	0.000	2.018	0.405	0.509	0.000	0.226	0.628	1.426	1,062.745
Other children	0.020	4.528	0.907	0.668	0.452	0.749	1.187	2.206	474.103
Toddlers	0.023	3.335	0.786	0.531	0.406	0.689	1.018	1.895	546.857

In Figure 4.5 the exposure of each population class is shown. It was found that toddlers, other children and adolescents had two- or three-times higher exposure than adults due to their

lower body weight. Although, infants consume less food contaminated with Acrylamide, they showed high exposure because they have the lowest body weight. It was found from the consumption data that other children and adolescents had the higher consumption of fried potatoes and potato chips, products with high concentrations of Acrylamide. On the other hand, toddlers have a low body weight, but they are in the age that consume products from all food categories. These results are very similar to the EFSA findings.

Figure 4.5: Mean Exposure by Population Class at MB scenario.

4.5 Mean Exposure at the MB scenario by [population class and area]

Figures 4.6 illustrate the mean exposure to Acrylamide by population class and geographical area. It was found that there is no significant difference between the geographical areas in all population classes. The exposure seems to be independent of the geographical area. This is because the population in Cyprus has the same food consumption habits and the foodstuffs that are contaminated by Acrylamide are consumed by all population classes.

Figure 4.6: Cross Plot

4.6 Contributions of different food groups to the dietary exposure

The contribution of each main food group to the total Acrylamide exposure is shown in Figure 4.7. Fried potatoes (37%), bread (8%), cereal flakes (7%), crisps/ships (6.8%), roast potatoes (6%) and biscuits (4.9%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the Acrylamide intake. These results are consistent to the EFSA findings.

Figure 4.7 shows the contribution of food items at FoodEx Level 4

Figure 4.7: Contribution to the Acrylamide Total Exposure MB.

Table 4.6: Contribution to the Acrylamide Total Exposure (MB). Food items at FoodEx2 Level 4 with greater than 1% contribution

Level1	Level2	Level3	Level4	Contribution
Grains and grain-based products	Bread and similar products	Crackers and breadsticks	Crackers and breadsticks	1.36%
Grains and grain-based products	Bread and similar products	Rusk	Rusk	1.98%
Grains and grain-based products	Bread and similar products	Unleavened or flat bread and similar	Traditional unleavened breads	1.29%
Grains and grain-based products	Bread and similar products	Leavened bread and similar	Wheat bread and rolls	7.98%
Grains and grain-based products	Bread and similar products	Leavened bread and similar	Sandwich bread (hamburger roll-type)	1.65%
Grains and grain-based products	Fine bakery wares	Biscuits	Biscuits, sweet, plain	3.67%
Grains and grain-based products	Fine bakery wares	Biscuits	Biscuit with inclusions, filling or coating	4.92%

Level1	Level2	Level3	Level4	Contribution
Grains and grain-based products	Breakfast cereals	Processed and mixed breakfast cereals	Popped cereals	1.69%
Grains and grain-based products	Breakfast cereals	Processed and mixed breakfast cereals	Cereal flakes and similar	7.02%
Starchy roots or tubers and products thereof, sugar plants	Starchy roots and tubers	Potatoes and similar-	Potatoes {Boiling}	2.67%
Starchy roots or tubers and products thereof, sugar plants	Starchy roots and tubers	Potatoes and similar-	Potatoes {Frying}	37.01%
Starchy roots or tubers and products thereof, sugar plants	Starchy roots and tubers	Potatoes and similar-	Potatoes {Roasting}	5.99%
Coffee, cocoa, tea and infusions	Hot drinks and similar (coffee, cocoa, tea and herbal infusions)	Coffee beverages	Coffee beverages	2.06%
Coffee, cocoa, tea and infusions	Hot drinks and similar (coffee, cocoa, tea and herbal infusions)	Coffee beverages	Coffee espresso (beverage)	1.29%
Coffee, cocoa, tea and infusions	Hot drinks and similar (coffee, cocoa, tea and herbal infusions)	Coffee beverages	Coffee with milk or cream	1.32%
Food products for young population	Processed cereal-based food for infants and young children	Cereals with an added high protein food reconstituted	Cereals with an added high protein food reconstituted	1.61%
Composite dishes	Dishes, incl. Ready to eat meals (excluding soups and salads)	Dishes excluding pasta or rice dishes, sandwiches and pizza	Meat based dishes	1.26%
Composite dishes	Fried or extruded cereal, seed or root-based products	Snacks other than chips and similar	Mixed cereal-based snacks	2.36%
Composite dishes	Fried or extruded cereal, seed or root-based products	Chips, crisps, fries and dough-based analogues	Chips/crisps	6.79%

5 Uncertainties

The evaluation of the uncertainties in the exposure assessment of acrylamide has been performed following the guidance of the Opinion of the Scientific Committee related to Uncertainties in Dietary Exposure Assessment. Table 5.1 presents a summary of uncertainties, highlighting the main sources of uncertainty and providing an estimate whether each source of uncertainty is likely to lead to an over- or under-estimation of the calculated dietary exposure.

Table 5.1: Summary of qualitative evaluation of the impact of uncertainties on the dietary exposure to acrylamide.

Sources of uncertainty	Direction ¹
Different time frame between concentration data and consumption data	+/-
Lack of information in the consumption data on the way potato, bread and coffee are prepared	+/-
Long-term (chronic) exposure assessed from few days of consumption	+
Measurement error in amounts of food consumed	+/-
Measurement error in individual body weights	+/-
Assumptions taken into account for the preparation of occurrence data	+/-
Level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy for the calculation of the exposure	+

¹ + = uncertainty with potential to cause over-estimation of exposure; - = uncertainty with potential to cause under-estimation of exposure

A number of uncertainties can be identified regarding the selection of parameters, such as acrylamide concentration levels in foodstuffs and consumption data.

The uncertainty related to the representativeness of the occurrence data for certain food commodities with respect to the number of samples is taken into account. Given the fact that the analytical results were generated with mass spectrometry (MS) based methods in an accredited laboratory, this adds only slightly to the uncertainty of the analytical results.

The Food Consumption Database, lacks systematic information on how the foodstuffs (bread, potatoes, coffee) were prepared/cooked before consumption. Also there is no reporting on the consumers' preferences regarding the degree of potato frying and bread toasting, as well as the place of consumption of potato fried products. Previous studies showed clearly that there are significant differences in Acrylamide levels between differently prepared foods and between the different brands of the same food item, since Acrylamide concentration in food depend on how food is being processed and cooked. Some potentially important extrapolation uncertainties arise since an individual survey of food consumption is used to

estimate dietary exposure over a timescale longer than the survey duration. Remaining uncertainties relate to the measurement error in amounts of consumed foodstuffs and individual body weights.

In ImproRisk occurrence and consumption data matching for the calculation of the exposure is performed based on a level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy, which may lead to overestimation of the exposure.

Furthermore, several assumption taken into account in the preparation of the occurrence (data from EFSA, dilution factors, aggregation) data may lead to some uncertainties.

6 Conclusions

Mean dietary Acrylamide exposure of the Cypriot population was calculated as 0.41 and 1.19 µg/kg b.w./day for mean and high consumers, respectively. Current exposure levels of Cypriot population are not of health concern with regards to neurotoxicity, and indicate some concern for carcinogenicity.

There was no significant difference in Acrylamide intake between geographical areas and genders. It was found that toddlers, other children and adolescents had higher exposure values due to their lower body weight and their consumption habits.

Fried potatoes (37%), bread (8%), cereal flakes (7%), crisps/ships (6.8%), roast potatoes (6%) and biscuits (4.9%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the Acrylamide intake.

7 References

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8 Abbreviations

Table 8.1: Abbreviations

Key	Description
BMDL	Benchmark dose lower limit (lower bound of benchmark dose interval)
b.w.	Body weight
LB	Lower bound
LOD	Limit of detection
MB	Middle bound
MoE	Margin of exposure
SD	Standard deviation
P25	25th percentile
P75	75th percentile
P95	95th percentile
UB	Upper bound
wcoeff	Weight coefficient

9 Appendices